

Screenwriting Applied to the Academic Study of Religion: *Some Kind of Liberating Effect*, a Documentary on Central and Eastern Europe

Valerio Severino

1 The Raw Footage

A documentary on the history of the academic study of religion was released in September 2023.¹ The film explores the issue of the freedom of research in this field of study, as it is perceived and experienced in Central and Eastern Europe in the last fifty years.² The niche of the research-made-in-film was chosen to be positioned in this very region, as the question of freedom, for historical reasons, has various levels of meaning and considerations here; and as it is not only crucial to the discipline *per se* but is also understood to mean a political/ideological freedom that still is not considered as granted in these countries.

This contribution examines the making of the script for the documentary *Some Kind of Liberating Effect* (hereafter SKLE). This script elaborates on the material of twenty interviews with scholars of religion,³ filmed in nine countries

¹ Some previous documentaries on religious studies can be mentioned, such as *Mircea Eliade et la redécouverte du sacré* (Paul Barbă Neagră, 1987, 58 min. running time), or *Mircea Eliade: His Name, His Destiny* (Dan Jelesco, 2010, 85 min.); as well as the shorts filmed for the American Scholars of Religion – Video Collection (Alfred F. Benney, 1993–2012 [digital commons – Fairfield University, Connecticut]), including the most widely known short video interviews with Jonathan Z. Smith (1999); or the three shorts on Furio Jesi’s works (*Myth, Politics, History*, Alberto Toscano, 2021) sponsored by the Italian Cultural Institute of London; the collection of 400 podcasts recorded since 2012 featuring scholars of religions recorded by The Religious Studies Project, and others. An extended investigation of this subject is out of the bounds for this essay and requires much additional exploration and study. Further and fuller information in this respect will be presented in a separate essay.

² The documentary is the main output of a project supported by the European Commission within the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions program, called CROSS (Communication for Religious Studies), project 101032467, hosted by the Department of Sociology, Andragogy, and Cultural Anthropology at the Palacký University Olomouc.

³ The interviewees, listed in alphabetical order: Milda Ališauskienė, Madis Arukask, Audrius Beinorius, Tomáš Bubík, Eugen Ciurtin, Liudmyla Fylypovych, Maija Grizāne, Halina Grzymata-Moszczyńska, Dorota Hall, Mihály Hoppál, Oleg Kyselov, András Máté-Tóth, Tamás Nyirkos, Jānis Priede, Gergely László Rosta, Anita Stasulane, Alessandro Testa, Lech Trzcionkowski, David Václavík, Ülo Valk.

(Alabama [USA], Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, and Ukraine) between October 2022 and May 2023.⁴ All the participating scholars belong to the network of the International Association of the History of Religions (IAHR) and the European Association for the Study of Religions (EASR).

Each of the interviewees responds to some questions out of a set of ten,⁵ discussing the issue of the freedom of research from various angles. The ten questions had been formulated in advance, upon a theoretical exploration of the topic, the results of which were published (Severino 2022). These questions are not verbalized in the documentary. They had been given to the interviewees beforehand, rather to provide some guidelines that could give direction to how the discourse could develop. Therefore, the footage is not arranged thematically. The utterances are not grouped according to the questions they answer. Instead, the selected pieces have been sequenced to tell a story.

The shootings yielded 715 minutes of raw material, and this essay questions how this footage was selected and then organized for the end product of 51 minutes running time. This contribution examines the techniques used to

⁴ In the cities of Budapest, Szeged, Prague, Olomouc, Kraków, Warsaw, Vilnius, Riga, Tartu, Bucharest, Chernivtsi, and Tuscaloosa.

⁵ The questions were: (1) What led you to become a scholar interested in religion? Please, refer to the very first thing that sparked your interest. (2) What is your ideal of freedom of research? And/or what does it mean to you? (3) What do you consider the most impactful events (1 to 3) that have either promoted or hindered freedom in your country? Please, recall some personal memories, if any, related to these events. (4) Has the freedom of research undergone any changes in the last 50 years? (5) From what has the Academic Study of Religion to be free in order to be scientific? (6) Could you give your personal position on the claim “the freedom from theology represents the immediate goal of the Academic Study of Religion”? (7) A scientific approach may reach results or knowledge which are different from the dogma of a religion. What is your view concerning a confrontation, if any, between freedom of religion and freedom of academic studies? (8) Can you think of any circumstances/cases when an eventual conscious or subconscious self-restraint may limit the freedom of research in the Academic Study of Religion? (9) Do you believe in the authority of science (facts/data)? What kind of obedience to this authority do you consider acceptable and/or compulsory? (10) Please, share direct or indirect experiences, and/or state your views on the limits of access of women to religious knowledge in institutions affiliated and non-affiliated to Churches. The interviewees were asked to choose 3–5 questions to elaborate on, which they wished to answer. This way, their choices also represent an approach, inasmuch as their selected topics express what arguments they considered relevant for the understanding of “freedom of research.”

develop a script on the history of the academic study of religion. These techniques, on the one hand, served as a tool of postproduction, on the other they helped reveal and notice certain aspects that could otherwise have gone unnoticed by the larger audience and nonspecialized public.

The subsequent parts of this essay address each of the three acts of the script more closely. Then, an examination of the frame story of the film will follow. This essay concludes with an evaluation of the interdisciplinary and intersectoral approaches implemented, and some remarks about the contents of the interviews.

2 Screenwriting Techniques

In this section, I will demonstrate how SKLE integrates screenwriting with the academic study of religion. In other words, I shall dwell on its interdisciplinary approach to the question of freedom of research to the extent that the raw material of the interviews with scholars fits the narrative blueprints used by professional screenwriters. It should be noted that the documentary does apply scriptwriting techniques to the raw footage for plotting a story. To structure its script, it has adopted methods largely employed in the filmmaking industry. Not only does the documentary have a three-act structure that generally characterizes feature films, but it complies with a schematic that both maps out the key elements of film storytelling and outlines in what order these elements/events should occur, that is, the timing of when these elements should happen.

In preproduction, the screenplay models I am referring to are intended as “formulas” or “forms” to fill, or, as screenwriters label it, a “Beat Sheet” that breaks down each act into a target number of scenes and fractions of scenes (beats) to be identified and included. I do not intend to present this as a complete picture of current screenwriting but as a fair sketch. This means that I will limit my examination to a foundational set of models that have been proposed and endorsed by experts such as Egri (1923), Field (1979), Snyder (2007), Hauge (2011), Calvisi (2012), Edson (2012), Fink (2014), and Chamberlain (2016), just to

mention a few.⁶ I aim to discuss only SKLE points relevant to the examination. Therefore, some specific key elements of the screenplay will be listed below, which account for the interdisciplinary approach of the documentary and have a bearing on its script. In the following, I shall elaborate in more detail on how the filmed raw material developed into beats of a story structure, and finally matched the characteristics that go with these beats.

The documentary starts with a theme statement (“Half of my life happened before ... the freedom of society” [Máté-Tóth]), setting the tone and establishing the order of the world (where and when). To this aim, the film selects parts of the interviews that establish the beginning of the story: “I have spent my youth in a country that was called Soviet Union” (Valk); “I grew up in a Communist country” (Nyirkos); “I am a product of the Soviet Union” (Stasulane). An introduction/overview of some of the protagonists is provided by means of a jump-cut sequence of the interviewees in the shooting sets, which serves as an opening. This is only a visual familiarization, as the figures of the interviewees appear, but at this point without any specific information on them. The opening includes a hook too, which is an anticipation of the frame story that I will refer to in greater detail in the following section. The hook scene is a shot of a lake shore and presents a match-cut: the camera rotates up to the point when the shoreline is seen in a diagonal position so that it corresponds to the diagonal line that also appears in the next shot, namely the interview located in a library. The bases of the bookshelves on the left have the same visual given before by the shoreline in a diagonal position.

Act 1 introduces what in screenwriting is called the “set-up want,” which is presented soon after the opening of the first scene. Here, it is verbalized by the protagonists, and inspires the title of the documentary: “some kind of liberating effect” is a quotation from one of the interviewees, the Estonian Ülo Valk, who refers to his experience reading a religious text the “Dhammapada”

⁶ In the following, I am going to use the technical terms developed in screenwriting as used and explained in these reference works, without specific bibliographical references in each case, as they are common and widely used in professional screenplay.

from the Buddhist Pali Canon, that provided a “reading” of the real-life circumstances under Communist oppression, and an ideal of an opposition.

The study of religion – Valk goes on – “represented some kind of alternative knowledge.” In like manner, the Catholic Church was perceived as “a kind of center of anti-Soviet resistance” in Lithuania (Beinorius). The free study of religion drives the protagonists’ motivation both to get rid of Communism and to oppose its efforts made at demonstrating that “religion is disappearing from the consciousness of Soviet people” (Stasulane), regarding the implementation of scientific atheism in the USSR and Warsaw Pact countries.

In the second half of the first act, the “inciting incident” takes place – the rules of screenwriting define this incident as a key element of Act 1. It always introduces an unforeseen event, also called a “catch,” which leads to clarifying what is at stake in the goal of the protagonists and the “set-up want.” This leading and dramatic question is intended as a “point of no return” and incites a strong movement forward. In this documentary, statements concerning some limits of Communist oppression, and inauthentic Communist un-freedom, are selected as the catch. This limitation is understood through allusions to the complexity of repression, culminating in the following statements: It was possible to “survive without making compromises” under Communism (Nyirkos); or “in small circles, it was possible to discuss ... I don’t think that ideological constraints ... actually limits research freedom so much” (Valk); and “It’s not possible to erase freedom from people’s life” (Václavík). Then, the stakes are raised – according to the practice of screenwriters, who up the ante already at the end of Act 1 – by breaking down and considering different phases of Communism in Central and Eastern Europe, particularly the era of reforms and protests included in a period that is referred to as “the last years of Communism” (Nyirkos). Such statements as “Nothing [i.e. no retributions for underground meetings] happened” (Hoppál), and “I never witnessed this sort of events [i.e. censorship, control over scientific research]” (Grzymała-Moszczyńska), and referring to the repression of the Catholic Church, “This does not apply to Poland so much” (Hall), are examples of a script process based on creating striking contrast, and

show how the story develops the other way around.

Act 2 is a classic example of what screenwriting intends as “conflict escalation.”

In this part, the plan laid out in the set-up want should be, and is here, destroyed. This part is meant to start with a first major obstacle, casualty, or setback, and arrive at a “failure”; what was seen in the first part as an established safe identity is threatened in this one. The jargon refers to this sequence as the “dark night,” which leads to a midpoint, after which an “all is lost” crisis develops. The documentary plunges into the dark night with references such as to “the aftermath of the Romanian revolution of December 1989” as a “radical, confusing, perplexing ... and very enigmatic type of freedom” (Ciurtin), and statements that represent the setback such as “I will not be so sure ... that [today] we have complete freedom of religious studies” (Beinorius). Screenwriting views this stage as one where the protagonists have reached their goal or “want,” but only in its external sense, not in essence. Here, one witnesses this phase in such reflections as: “Is there still a question about the freedom of academy? Because we are no more persecuted. ... Science ... is marginalized. ... It is like the make-up” (Máté-Tóth).

This series of puzzling-startling utterances brings the audience to the midpoint, climaxing in upside-down kinds of statement: “The old seed of space for freedom, Church, began to be perceived as a source of repression” (Trzcionkowski), and “In Soviet times there were ... dogmas everywhere ... but surprisingly it somehow ... made people feel free [i.e. as points of reference, to which one could adapt themselves]. But today ... seemingly, there are not too many limits, and people ... tend to lose themselves. ... Freedom is very absolute, but ...” (Arukask). This is a complete reversal from the initial set-up want in Act 1, which was, to put it simply, to eliminate Communism for freedom.

The “all is lost” part of Act 2 paints a dark post-1989/1991 picture with statements such as “My experience is a narrowing of academic freedom” (Rosta) and “Paradigm shifts can claim their victims” (Testa), or “I am not really sure whether the next generation has still this question [i.e. of freedom]” (Máté-Tóth). The second section of Act 2 is described by screenwriters through

the imagery of archery, by referring to the drawing of the bowstring back to its point of utmost tension, which is a preparation for the launching of something new – which will be Act 3. In SKLE this point of maximum intensity is reached with the following: “A dangerous tendency is the rise of political populism” and with “Academic study of religion might be endangered” (Ališauskienė), and others on the war in Ukraine: “[Due to the] infra-Christian ... polemic between ... Patriarch Kirill of Moscow and the religious authorities of Ukraine, doing history of religions, academic study of religions, religious studies even, it is almost impossible” (Ciurtin) or along the same lines, the testimony of an Ukrainian scholar of religion filmed in Alabama: “Some people in Ukraine would like to ban” the Ukrainian Orthodox Church. As before 2022 it had been a part of the Russian Orthodox Church, so now it could be seen as “one of the centers of the spread of Russian world ideology. Those who claim that the ban can’t be implemented because of the right of freedom of religion are labeled as ‘pro-Russian agents’ or ‘agents of FSB’” (Kyselov). The audience is informed of the evolving narrative of opposition to Russia, that is, from Russian atheism in Soviet times to Russian Christian Orthodoxy today.

Act 3 is the resolution and brings the conflict to an end. The resolving arc movement covers the entire transformation, starting from the “fight for freedom” formula set up in Act 1, its crisis described in Act 2, and eventually the final lack of formula as it is framed in the following lines: “Freedom is a quite tricky term” (Hoppál), “I don’t think that freedom is something binary” (Nyirkos), or “We have a system, but democrats we should become” (Bubík). In Act 3 the protagonists reach the true “point of no return.” Screenwriters refer to it as a “burn the bridge behind” moment. Accordingly, in SKLE the interviewees go so far as to insist that it is “not only the persecution” of churches during the forty years of atheist ideology in former Communist lands that has led religion to decline (Rosta). The final act leads to a “turn in direction” by considering the inverted new order of persecution, that is, the persecution of atheists, which turns the persecution of the churches in Soviet times (by the atheists) upside-down, with reference to “scholars of religions

who have to run from [Islamic] countries” because of their “atheistic standpoints” (Grzymata-Moszczyńska). A political new order is presented as well with regard to “new problems” of scholars of religion “in such countries like Russia, even like the United States” where “there is a visible and strong pressure from some public stakeholders ... to influence religious studies by some concrete ideology ... rooted in some religious system” (Václavík).

The “ultimate theme” or “final step,” is reached by presenting an “assumption of power” by science over itself: “The science is so strong, and I’m optimistic that the science will be very successful in solving these problems” (Václavík).

There is also a “learn the lesson” moment and “beauty in the struggle” aspects in the bottom line of the documentary: “Freedom ... always has some limits and always has some unlimited versions on how to transgress boundaries” (Hoppál). In screenwriting, the “finale” is the opposite of the “flaw” in the protagonist’s story arc. In the context of the documentary, this can be interpreted as the limits of freedom and how they relate as well to the “flaw” in Act 2, which deals with the defense and reversal of these limits since 1989. The protagonists ultimately highlight the strength of a critique of these limits as they advocate for a nonbinary, unlimited approach to freedom.

3 Frame Story: from History to Storytelling

The documentary film combines twenty different interviews by switching back and forth, highlighting complementary perspectives. Additionally, it includes a short frame story that serves as a companion piece to the main narrative by supplementing it with a fictional interview.

The short features the actress Kata Sarbó as Johanna Katona, a fictional Hungarian scholar of religion, and tells the story of the day of the shooting, showing what happens before, behind the scenes, during the interview on the shooting set, and in the interviewee’s mind. It develops into a story of eleven parts, alternating between reality and fiction. After each scene of the frame story a new sequence of actual interviews follows.

The goal of the frame story is to create an atmosphere of disorientation and

uncertainty, which it achieves on different levels. On the one hand, there is a shifting between reality and dream, on the other, some visual cues evoke a strong sense of imbalance. As an example for the former level, we may mention the doubling of the protagonist (when she sees herself floating in a lake).

As for the latter level, the final and progressive camera rotation of 90 degrees clockwise could be pointed out, when the camera turns on its axis, and the horizontal line of the lake slowly revolves until it becomes vertical, having the protagonist floating in the middle of the (now) upright water line.

The underlying “geometrics” do not only work on a horizontal-vertical level but also the spins around the axis might be considered. To continue the scene described above, we may refer to the following aerial shot that shows the protagonist from above, floating. The camera drone rises, then stops when she is in the middle of the picture, and here, the image of a rotating carillon dancer fades in and blends with the protagonist floating in the water.

The visual cues come from the subtext of the fairy tale *The Steadfast Tin Soldier* by Hans Christian Andersen, which informs the short. It provides images of the one-legged soldier and the spinning ballerina. The short makes visual references to these, in the form of a framed print that is a drawing taken from an illustrated edition of Andersen’s tales (*Caught by a Fish* [Andersen 1933]), the carillon dancer, and the origami ship. The name of the protagonist of the frame story, Johanna Katona, is also a cue: Katona means soldier in Hungarian. In addition to this, her line in the course of the interview “I wonder how people, scholars, continue to stand like on one leg without losing what I feel to be or would call maybe their balance, or their trying to be in balance” is a hidden quotation from *The Steadfast Tin Soldier*.⁷

Two of the visual cues, namely the origami ship and the print (that depicts the Steadfast Tin Soldier after his fall from the paper ship just at the moment when he is about to be swallowed by the fish), evoke the waterfall scene of

⁷ “Then he laid himself at full length on the table behind a snuff-box that stood upon it, so that he could peep at the little delicate lady, who continued to stand on one leg without losing her balance” (Andersen 1888: 26).

the fairy tale that, because of its verticality, is a parallel of the vertical floating of the protagonist in the short. Moreover, while the fairy tale ends with the soldier and the ballerina joining in the fire, in this scene, the figures of Katona (soldier) and the ballerina come together in the water, blending harmoniously. It is worth mentioning that in the desk scene, where the origami ship is featured, there is also a book with the fictional title of *Freedom of Research in the Academic Study of Religion* that introduces the theme of the documentary to the audience in a subtle way. The cover displays a photograph of an acrobat crossing the Danube on a tightrope.⁸ This image also contributes to the visual theme of fragile balance.

In one scene at the protagonist's home, a TV broadcasts images of the war in Ukraine, in the background are demolished houses and missing walls in blocks of apartments that let the viewers see destroyed internal settings of flats. Some images present a pile of books on a table, suggesting that some scholarly activity was disrupted there. In the foreground, a carillon dancer rotates to the beat of the song *Rise of Times* (Martini 2023) while the background TV displays images of a descent from the top of a fire damaged building, one floor at a time. These contemporaneous movements are intended to set in motion a kind of Kuleshov effect, transferring the emotional response of the audience to the video of burned buildings to the carillon dancer, investing this rotating object with the emotions felt while watching the footage (Kondrashev 2023), mediated by the facial expression of the protagonist watching the sequence of images on TV. The televised video finally resonates with a nearby illustration from Andersen's tale. The camera pans across the scene, ultimately focusing on a framed print of the one-legged tin soldier of the fairy tale sinking in the water, visually echoing the descent from a burnt building we just witnessed. In the next scene, this emotional response is then transferred from the carillon dancer to the protagonist floating in the water as the figure of the rotating ballerina fades in. This effect is an editing technique used in the film documentary

⁸ László Simet, performance in Budapest, April 2023.

to visually connect the personal story of the scholar with the ongoing recent events in Eastern Europe.

The frame story provides context for the real interviews, suggesting that behind every shooting there is a personal story to explore, and creating a cohesive narrative. On the other hand, given that a declared goal of the film project was to communicate the results of this research to a wider, nonspecialized audience, this frame story is also used to establish connection. By deliberately not dwelling on academic research and scientific results, the frame story provides a personal atmosphere to which the viewer can relate. It is an output of science communication, and, as such, its goal is to reach the general public rather than document or relate strictly to the discipline. The frame story is included in a documentary that goes beyond the history of public institutions and scientific production in the academic study of religion. It delves into storytelling and implements a shift from the strict historiographical format. In doing so, the documentary seeks to move over the limits and barriers of the academic debate, to hook and engage viewers who are unlikely to watch purely academic lessons.

4 Concluding Remarks: Interdisciplinary and Intersectoral Approaches

This article examines how screenwriting techniques were applied to the academic study of religion in a documentary that explores freedom of research in this very field. It is to be noted that the documentary develops not only an interdisciplinary approach but also aims at achieving an intersectoral collaboration between religious studies and the film industry. By intersectoral, I mean that scholars of religion actively participate as screenwriters, filmmakers, and executive producers, not just as consultants in preproduction. The documentary can be considered as a pilot film that shows the potential and the prospects of commercial broadcast, and eventually the exploitation of the

film industry by the academic study of religion on a larger scale.⁹

As a further step to explore in future research, we may also pose the question of whether the techniques of screenwriting/script can be used in the discipline of the academic study of religion, providing an alternative to academic writing by lending these tools for the arrangement and presentation of material.

As far as the specific contents of the documentary and its script are concerned, their review in the second section of this article has pointed out that in the past thirty years, there has been a – what screenwriting would call – “change of plan”: at the end of the 1980s and the beginning of the 1990s, the aim was to become free in a political sense, that is from an oppressing regime. Lately, becoming free may be regarded at various levels, and a lack of a single interpretation and uniform formula is evident.

At a post-screening debate held on February 6, 2024, at the Danube Institute, a Budapest-based conservative think tank, political scientist David Martin Jones challenged this conclusion. Jones focused on the film’s arc of the story, which starts with the Communist experience. For those who “were religious under a Communist regime,” Jones explained, and “were forced into an atheistic mindset,” rejecting it offered a “sense of freedom.” However – Jones went on – “the story that moves on is that after ’89.” Many scholars interviewed seem to “get lost in a post-modernist de-construction of everything,” neglecting “that there is still something central in religion that gives us what was historically a sense of freedom in the West” (Jones 2023: 32:00–33:45).

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⁹ However, SKLE was released as open access to comply with the rules of the European Commission, the funding organization of the film (MSCA, Horizon 2020, project CROSS n. 101032467).

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Numen 71 (20 24) 599–611

Severino, Valerio S. 2023. "Discourses on Research Freedom in the Academic Study of Religion: An Overview." *Method and Theory in the Study of Religion* 36(1): 1–20. doi.org/10.1163/15700682-bja10107.

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Funding

Funded by the European Commission: MSCA, Horizon 2020, project CROSS n. 101032467.

Published in the Journal:

Numen 71 (20 24) 599–611